

Original Research

Role of Personal Attributes in Consumers' Green Purchase Intentions: The Moderating Effect of Price Sensitivity

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15446551>**Abstract**

This study investigates the psychological and economic factors influencing green purchase intentions (GPI) in Turkmenistan, focusing on the moderating role of price sensitivity (PS). Data from 388 respondents were collected, and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) was employed for analysis. The findings reveal that environmental awareness (EA), perceived self-efficacy (PSE), self-identity (SI), and subjective norms (SN) significantly influence GPI. PSE positively affects GPI, emphasizing the role of consumer confidence in making environmentally responsible choices. While SN exhibits a mixed effect, it remains a key predictor of GPI, underscoring the impact of social expectations on sustainable behavior. Additionally, price sensitivity moderates the relationship between self-identity and GPI, though no significant moderating effect is observed between EA and GPI. These insights offer valuable implications for policymakers and marketers, emphasizing the need to address affordability concerns and leverage psychological factors to promote green purchasing in emerging markets.

Keywords: Environmental Awareness, Subjective Norms, Self-Identity, Perceived Self-Efficacy, Green Purchase Intention, Price Sensitivity

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Introduction

In recent decades, the increasing environmental concerns have brought sustainability to the forefront of global discussions. The accelerating pace of climate change, driven by unsustainable consumption and production habits, poses threats to ecosystems, human health, and socioeconomic stability. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2022) recognizes the need to limit global warming to 1.5°C to avoid catastrophic consequences, requiring urgent collective action across sectors, including a shift in consumer behavior. Over the years, several challenges that include climate change, biodiversity loss, resource depletion, and pollution from plastic have raised the importance of sustainable consumption (Lee, 2020). Issues raised have propelled consumers, businesses, and policymakers into green consumerism. Green consumerism is a type of purchasing behavior that helps reduce environmental damage through environmentally friendly choices (Nguyen et al., 2021). This type of purchasing behavior means a great deal to

sustainability in environmental management, as this enables consumers to address issues related to environmental sustainability by consuming organic products, renewable energy, and goods from companies that are said to follow a minimum degree of green.

It's noted that the rise in green consumption reflects a growing green purchase intention (GPI), which refers to an individual's motivation to buy environmentally friendly products and the increasing adoption of green purchasing behaviors (Yue et al., 2019). According to Ahmad and Zhang (2020), green purchasing extends beyond the mere act of buying, it encompasses the entire consumption cycle - from purchase to post-consumption disposal and recycling. This comprehensive approach emphasizes long-term sustainability rather than one-time transactions. Similarly, Paul, Modi, and Patel (2016) define green purchase intention as a conscious decision to purchase eco-friendly products or support brands that minimize environmental harm. Thus, GPI is widely recognized as a central element of green purchasing behavior (GPB), as it reflects the transition from intention to actual behavior.

Green purchase intention (GPI) is influenced by several psychological and social factors. Joshi and Rahman (2019) discussed the main antecedents to GPI which included environmental awareness, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and personal norms. Supporting Joshi and Rahman's findings, Ramadhanti et al. (2024) stated when the individuals became more aware of environment issues, they had a better attitude towards green products, which increased their GPI. Similarly, Despotović (2021) emphasized that growing environmental awareness fuels broader societal shifts, including stronger regulatory frameworks and increased corporate commitment to sustainability.

Among these determinants, subjective norms play a role in influencing GPI by reflecting the expectations and approval of others (Ramadhanti et al. 2024; Wang & Yang, 2023). Consumers have a tendency to imitate sustainable behaviors of other members in the social environment to gain social acceptance, whether through purchasing eco-friendly products or reducing waste (Onwezen, 2014).

In addition to social influences, prior studies have identified self-identity as a significant factor influencing GPI, suggesting that individuals who align themselves with pro-environmental values are more likely to engage in sustainable consumption behaviors (Grębosz-Krawczyk et al., 2021). Consistently, Mishra, Shukla, and Malhotra (2023) showed that individuals with a well-developed green self-identity are significantly more inclined to choose eco-friendly products, highlighting the motivational power of identity.

Furthermore, studies have found that perceived self-efficacy significantly influences GPI, particularly the belief that one can make a meaningful difference for the environment - commonly referred to as environmental self-efficacy. This belief helps them overcome external barriers, such as limited product availability or social discouragement (Yoong et al., 2018). As Geiger (2019) emphasized, individuals who feel confident in their ability to make a difference not only adopt green behaviors themselves but also inspire others within their social circles to do the same. This collective sense of empowerment opens the door to broader societal engagement and action toward sustainability.

Although numerous psychological and social variables have been identified as significant predictors of GPI, their influence is not always sufficient to drive consistent sustainable consumption. The presence of these favorable factors often fails to translate into actual purchasing behavior due to competing priorities and contextual barriers. Recent studies highlighted that even environmentally conscious consumers may experience conflicting motivations when faced with practical constraints such as price, limited product availability, or lack of trust in green product claims (Joshi & Rahman, 2019; Mishra et al., 2023). For instance, Nguyen et al. (2021) argued that while positive environmental attitudes are crucial, situational variables - particularly financial considerations can override intentions and reduce the likelihood of green purchases. Similarly, Liobikiėnė and Bernatoniėnė (2022) emphasized that in emerging markets, economic factors often dilute the strength of psychological drivers, resulting in a gap between consumers' values and their actual behavior. These shifts in attitudes reflect a broader increase in global environmental awareness. The Capgemini Research Institute (2021) reported that 79% of global consumers are willing to adjust their buying behavior based on environmental and social impact. However, despite this growing awareness, a persistent attitude-behavior gap remains. The same Capgemini study found that only 10% of consumers regularly purchase environmentally friendly products, highlighting a disconnect between consumers' stated values and their actual behaviors (Zhumagulova, 2023). This gap is often attributed to various obstacles including limited availability, convenience, skepticism, and especially price sensitivity.

This issue is even more relevant in developing economies, where economic and contextual factors may inhibit green purchasing. While sustainability-related research is growing in Central Asia, especially in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, (Khabibullina & Borissov, 2021), there remains limited research on consumer-level green behavior in Turkmenistan. Existing studies have primarily addressed areas such as infrastructure development (Penjiyev, 2024), industrial reforms (Meshcheryakov, 2019), renewable energy (Satymov & Bogdanov, 2021), climate change (Myradov et al., 2024), and waste management (Korostova, 2020; Orazov et al., 2024). While these government-led sustainability efforts have an indirect influence on public attitudes, few studies have directly examined green purchase intention or the psychological and financial factors influencing consumer decisions in this context.

Among these factors, price sensitivity stands out as a crucial economic consideration in developing markets. The

financial constraints faced by many consumers, along with the perceived premium prices of green products, influence their purchasing decisions. Despite increasing awareness and interest in green products, the cost barrier remains a significant challenge for many consumers in developing markets, preventing them from translating their green purchase intentions into actual behavior. Therefore, understanding how price sensitivity interacts with other psychological and social variables is essential to uncovering the critical drivers of GPI in the region.

This study aims to fill this gap by examining the psychological, social, and financial factors that influence GPI in Turkmenistan, with a particular focus on price sensitivity as a moderating variable. Drawing on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the research explores how environmental awareness, subjective norms, and self-identity affect green purchasing intentions, and how price sensitivity shapes these relationships. The objectives of this study are outlined as follows:

- ✧ Explore how psychological and social variables are related to green purchase intention.
- ✧ Assess the role of price sensitivity as a moderator in green purchase intention.
- ✧ Provide additional empirical contributions on consumer behavior in the context of sustainability in Turkmenistan.

The present study brings theory closer to empirical evidence and thereby adds to the common knowledge about GPI concerning emerging economies and offers some important hints for policy makers and businesses toward sustainable consumption.

Fig.1: Proposed research model

Based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and supported by previous empirical studies, a set of hypotheses has been developed to examine the relationships between psychological, social, and economic factors influencing green purchase intention. The study hypothesizes that environmental awareness (EA), subjective norms (SN), self-identity (SI), and perceived self-efficacy (PSE) positively influence green purchase intention (GPI), while price sensitivity (PS) moderates these relationships.

H1: Environmental awareness positively influences green purchase intention.

H2: Subjective norms positively influence green purchase intention.

H3: Self-identity positively influences green purchase intention.

H4: Perceived self-efficacy positively influences green purchase intention.

H5: Price sensitivity negatively moderates the relationships between environmental

The conceptual framework illustrating these hypothesized relationships is presented in Figure 1.

Materials and Methods

This study relies on Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as its theoretical approach to examine consumer behaviors. TPB has widely been the theoretical approach for examining pro-environmental behavior (Ghali-Zinoubi & Toukabri, 2019; Dubey et al., 2024) and posits that three predictors determine behavioral action: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. To enhance its explanatory power, this study extends TPB by incorporating

environmental awareness, self-identity, subjective norms, and perceived self-efficacy as independent variables, with price sensitivity serving as a moderating factor.

A quantitative research design was used to assess the influence of these measures on GPI using responses obtained from 388 respondents through convenience sampling, during the period of October to November 2024. The respondents were primarily of Turkmen ethnicity and lived in or were studying in China. A structured, self-administered questionnaire was distributed using Google Forms to obtain responses based on a five-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). The constructs and their measurement items were adapted from previously validated constructs (Ahmed et al., 2020; Minbashrazgah et al., 2017; Graveline et al., 2022; Yoong et al., 2018; Ghali-Zinoubi et al., 2019; Ayoun & Challab, 2017).

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used to assess the relationships developed from the above variables. The PLS approach was chosen to model the complex model in exploratory research that examines relationships with a focus on prediction instead of model fit (Hair et al., 2019). SmartPLS 4.0 software was used to assess the measurement model and structural model using reliability, validity, path coefficients, and moderating effects, while the SPSS Version 16.0 was used to analyze descriptive demographic data.

In terms of demographics, 55.4% were females and 53.9% of respondents were between 29–39 years old, and 33.5% of respondents were 18–28 years old, indicating a relatively young sample. Most of the respondents held a bachelor’s degree (48.5 %), while 27.1 % indicated completion of a Masters or above - demonstrating higher levels of educational attainment. In terms of employment, 41.8 % indicated they were employed while 22.4 % were self-employed. About 60% of the respondents lived in capital cities, where access to sustainable products and exposure to environmental campaigns may be enhanced factors, as higher levels of eco-consumerism could be expected (Altharthey, 2019). The income of participants was reasonably stable with roughly 28.1% of participants earning 3001 – 5000 manat, and 26.5 % reporting earnings of 5001 – 10,000 manat. The above demographic information provides useful context when interpreting patterns of green purchase intention within the sample.

The adequacy of sample size was confirmed using the formula provided by Tabachnick and Fidell (2007): $N > 50 + 8m$ where m = number of predictors. With a total of five independent variables, the minimum number of sample size is 90, and 388 respondents exceeded this threshold enabled behaviours expected to yield statistical power.

Results

To ensure the robustness of the measurement model, both reflective and formative constructs were examined for reliability and validity. The reflective constructs consisted of Environmental Awareness (EA), Subjective Norms (SN), Self-Identity (SI), Perceived Self-Efficacy (PSE), and Green Purchase Intention (GPI). Price Sensitivity (PS) was modeled as a formative construct, as its indicators describe different aspects of sensitivity to pricing, such as willingness to pay more for eco-friendly options or responsiveness to price changes.

The reflective constructs demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency. All the Cronbach’s Alpha values exceeded 0.70, the lowest Cronbach’s Alpha value was 0.769. Composite Reliability values consisted of 0.851 or higher evidencing high reliability. Convergent validity, measured using Average Variance Extracted (AVE), showed values above the 0.50 minimum, ranging from 0.588 upwards (Hair et al., 2017). The individual indicators also meet the item-level reliability as the loadings of each of the reflective construct’s indicators had loadings greater than 0.741, supporting its reliability. All these results suggest the measurement model is reliable and valid (see Table 1).

Table 1: Reliability and validity for reflective constructs

Constructs and indicators	Factor loadings	Average extracted variance (AVE)	Composite reliability	Cronbach’s Alpha
Environmental Awareness				
EA1	0.798	0.588	0.851	0.769
EA2	0.765			
EA3	0.752			
EA4	0.750			
Subjective Norms				
SN1	0.741	0.613	0.864	0.791
SN2	0.769			
SN3	0.814			

SN4	0.806			
Self-identity				
SI1	0.814			
SI2	0.885	0.736	0.918	0.886
SI3	0.846			
SI4	0.886			
Perceived self-efficacy				
PSE1	0.783			
PSE2	0.815			
PSE3	0.812	0.668	0.923	0.901
PSE4	0.857			
PSE5	0.864			
PSE6	0.769			
Price sensitivity				
PS1	0.822			
PS2	0.804	0.683	0.896	0.848
PS3	0.853			
PS4	0.826			
Green Purchase Intention				
GPI1	0.821			
GPI2	0.817	0.670	0.890	0.837
GPI3	0.798			
GPI4	0.839			

To assess discriminant validity, three methods were used: Cross-Loadings, Fornell-Larcker, and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). The Cross-Loadings analysis confirmed that each item loaded more strongly on its designated construct than on any other, supporting the distinctiveness of the constructs. According to the Fornell-Larcker criterion, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct should be greater than its correlations with other constructs. This condition was met for all constructs. For example, the square root of the AVE for Green Purchase Intention (GPI) was 0.819, which exceeded its highest inter-construct correlation of 0.368 with Perceived Self-Efficacy (PSE), as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Fornell- Larcker criterion

	EA	GPI	PS	PSE	SI	SN
EA	0.767					
GPI	0.125	0.819				
PS	0.032	0.332	0.826			
PSE	-0.021	0.368	0.424	0.818		
SI	-0.045	0.136	0.001	0.031	0.858	
SN	0.044	-0.165	-0.187	-0.126	0.030	0.783

HTMT ratios were all below the conservative threshold of 0.85, indicating strong discriminant validity. Notable examples include 0.151 between Environmental Awareness (EA) and GPI, and 0.469 between Price Sensitivity (PS) and PSE (see Table 3).

All these outcomes combined with Cross-Loadings, Fornell-Larcker, and HTMT ensure that all the constructs in the model are uniquely valid, ensuring they uniquely contribute to the model and reflect their theoretical foundations.

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio- Matrix

	EA	GPI	PS	PSE	SI	SN	PS x EA	PS x SN	PS x SI	PS x PSE
EA										
GPI	0.151									

PS		0.084	0.368							
PSE		0.075	0.410	0.469						
SI		0.080	0.148	0.065	0.096					
SN		0.069	0.195	0.216	0.156	0.051				
PS x EA	x	0.086	0.032	0.110	0.054	0.044	0.120			
PS x SN	x	0.108	0.226	0.456	0.267	0.097	0.048	0.126		
PS x SI		0.046	0.133	0.390	0.074	0.087	0.108	0.106	0.125	
PS x PSE	x	0.045	0.103	0.586	0.287	0.052	0.178	0.031	0.481	0.050

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values ranged between 1.482 and 3.353 (see Table 4), staying within acceptable bounds for both formative and reflective indicators, indicating no multicollinearity issues (Kock, 2015).

Table 4: Collinearity (VIF) – Outer model

	VIF
EA1	1.523
EA2	1.573
EA3	1.658
EA4	1.482
GPI1	1.691
GPI2	1.913
GPI3	1.869
GPI4	2.093
PS1	1.757
PS2	1.897
PS3	1.884
PS4	2.102
PSE1	1.924
PSE2	2.097
PSE3	2.118
PSE4	2.661
PSE5	2.798
PSE6	1.997
SI1	2.444
SI2	3.353
SI3	2.271
SI4	1.986
SN1	1.577
SN2	1.534
SN3	1.658
SN4	1.665
PS x EA	1.000
PS x SI	1.000
PS x SN	1.000
PS x PSE	1.000

Predictive relevance (Q^2) values were positive for all constructs, suggesting strong predictive power for GPI ($Q^2 = 0.444$), PS (0.465), PSE (0.500), and SI (0.540), and moderate relevance for EA (0.310) and SN (0.344) (see Table 7).

Table 5: Construct cross- validated communality

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
EA	1544.000	1065.331	0.310
GPI	1544.000	858.505	0.444
PS	1544.000	832.932	0.461
PSE	2316.000	1084.247	0.532
SI	1544.000	710.656	0.540
SN	1544.000	1012.451	0.344

The structural model explained 26.1% of the variance in Green Purchase Intention ($R^2 = 0.261$), indicating moderate explanatory power (Hair et al., 2019) (see Table 6).

Table 6: R-square and R-square adjusted

	R-square	R-square adjusted
GPI	0.261	0.243

Effect sizes (f^2) were small to moderate: PSE (0.068), PS (0.080), while EA (0.018), SI (0.025), and SN (0.011) showed smaller effects. Interaction terms had minimal impact ($PS \times EA = 0.008$; $PS \times SN = 0.001$). (see Table 7)

Table 7: F-square

	GPI
EA	0.018
GPI	
PS	0.080
PSE	0.068
SI	0.025
SN	0.011
PS x EA	0.008
PS x SN	0.001
PS x SI	0.034
PS x PSE	0.027

Fit indices were acceptable: SRMR = 0.059 (saturated), 0.060 (estimated), and NFI values were near 0.80 (see Table 8), supporting the model's adequacy.

Table 7: Model fit

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.059	0.060
d_ULS	1.218	1.271
d_G	0.420	0.424
Chi-square	968.865	984.417
NFI	0.803	0.800

The Hypothesis Testing and Moderating Effect

Following the validation of the measurement model, the structural model was assessed to examine the proposed hypotheses regarding the relationships between Environmental Awareness (EA), Subjective Norms (SN), Self-Identity (SI), Perceived Self-Efficacy (PSE), and Green Purchase Intention (GPI), as well as the moderating role of Price Sensitivity (PS). Path coefficients, T-statistics, and p-values were calculated using a bootstrapping procedure (5000 subsamples).

H1: Environmental awareness positively influences green purchase intention.

A positive and significant relationship was found between environmental awareness and green purchase intention ($\beta =$

0.119, T = 2.887, p = 0.004), consistent with Ahmed et al. (2020), and Rama et al (2023).

H2: Subjective norms positively influence green purchase intention.

Subjective norms had a negative but significant effect on green purchase intention ($\beta = -0.094$, T = 2.098, p = 0.036), supporting Minbashrazgah et al. (2017), who found that social pressures can sometimes discourage sustainable choices.

H3: Self-identity positively influences green purchase intention.

Self-identity exhibited a strong positive association with green purchase intention ($\beta = 0.138$, T = 2.715, p = 0.007), reinforcing findings by Gravelines et al. (2022) on the role of environmental self-identity in consumer behavior.

H4: Perceived self-efficacy positively influences green purchase intention.

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	Tstatistics (O/STDEV)	P values
EA -> GPI	0.119	0.128	0.041	2.887	0.004
PS -> GPI	0.360	0.354	0.067	5.365	0.000
PSE -> GPI	0.252	0.255	0.059	4.264	0.000
SI -> GPI	0.138	0.148	0.051	2.715	0.007
SN -> GPI	-0.094	-0.100	0.045	2.098	0.036
PS x EA -> GPI	0.085	0.080	0.056	1.506	0.132
PS x SN -> GPI	0.035	0.033	0.060	0.576	0.565
PS x SI -> GPI	-0.175	-0.162	0.060	2.914	0.004
PS x PSE -> GPI	0.108	0.107	0.043	2.533	0.011

Perceived self-efficacy had a highly significant impact on green purchase intention ($\beta = 0.252$, T = 4.264, p = 0.000), supporting Yoong et al. (2018), who emphasized the importance of confidence in sustainable decision-making (see Table 8).

Table 8: Direct relationship and moderation results

H5: Price sensitivity negatively moderates the relationships between environmental awareness, subjective norms, self-identity, perceived self-efficacy, and green purchase intention.

Price sensitivity significantly moderated the relationship between self-identity and green purchase intention ($\beta = -0.175$,

T = 2.914, p = 0.004). The negative interaction suggests that for highly price-sensitive consumers, the influence of self-identity on green purchasing diminishes. This supports previous findings that identity-driven intentions may be overridden by cost concerns (Ghali-Zinoubi & Toukabri, 2019).

The moderating effect of price sensitivity on the relationship between perceived self-efficacy and green purchase intention was positive and significant ($\beta = 0.108$, T = 2.533, p = 0.011). This indicates that consumers with strong self-efficacy remain committed to green purchases even when price is a concern—reflecting their confidence in managing sustainability challenges despite financial trade-offs (Dangelico & Vocalelli, 2017). No significant moderating effects were observed for the interactions between price sensitivity and either environmental awareness (p = 0.132) or subjective norms (p = 0.565). This suggests that the influence of these constructs on green purchase intention is relatively stable across different levels of price sensitivity (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Path coefficients

Discussion

This study examined the psychological and contextual factors influencing green purchase intention (GPI) in Turkmenistan, focusing on environmental awareness (EA), subjective norms (SN), self-identity (SI), perceived self-efficacy (PSE), and the moderating role of price sensitivity (PS). The findings confirm the applicability of the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991) in this context, while also highlighting critical contextual influences unique to emerging markets.

The positive effect of EA on GPI is consistent with previous studies suggesting that greater environmental awareness encourages sustainable purchasing behaviors (Ahmed et al., 2020; Ghali-Zinoubi & Toukabri, 2019; Rama et al., 2023). This finding supports the idea that awareness of ecological challenges, increases consumers' sense of responsibility, fostering a stronger commitment to eco-friendly behaviors. The significant role of EA in this context also reflects how education and access to environmental information can create more environmentally conscious consumers, influencing their decisions to prioritize sustainability in their purchasing habits. By raising awareness about environmental issues, individuals are more likely to view sustainability not as a trend but as a crucial aspect of their everyday choices, further promoting GPI.

The positive relationship between PSE and GPI was significantly strong and also supportive of the idea that individuals with the belief that they can have an impact with their consumption choices is a driving force for green behavior (Yoong et al, 2018; Dubey et al., 2024). PSE also explains the consumers' ability to act against barriers when considering price or limited product availability. In developing countries, where market constraints can limit access to eco-friendly products, PSE plays a crucial role in overcoming such challenges by fostering the belief that individual actions still matter. The stronger the belief that personal behavior can positively impact the environment, the more likely consumers are to

engage in sustainable purchasing, even when facing external constraints.

While the relationship between SN and GPI was statistically significant, its negative direction contradicts traditional TPB assumptions. This finding suggests that, in the context of this region, perceived social pressure may not always lead to pro-environmental behavior. In some cultural contexts, SN could be interpreted as resistance to green consumerism or a sense of skepticism towards eco-friendly practices, reflecting a misalignment with social norms around sustainability (Minbashrazgah et al., 2017). Therefore, there is a need for specific marketing strategies that would shift cultural perceptions and create social norms that encourage sustainable consumption.

The significant positive influence of SI on GPI is in line with previous findings that suggest individuals who perceive themselves as environmentally responsible are more likely to act in accordance with that identity (Gravelines et al., 2022; Grębosz-Krawczyk et al., 2021). Self-identity, especially when linked with moral values, is a key psychological driver of green consumption. This finding suggests that individuals who strongly identify as environmentally conscious are more likely to make green purchases, driven by their internalized environmental values. Additionally, the role of SI is further supported by recent studies that demonstrate how green self-identity contributes significantly to sustainable consumption behavior, especially in contexts where individuals see their actions as a reflection of their ethical beliefs and social responsibility (Kumar et al., 2023; Palomino Rivera & Barcellos-Paula, 2024). This could be particularly relevant in Turkmenistan, where green consumerism is still evolving, and self-identity linked to sustainability could be an emerging factor influencing GPI.

Importantly, the moderating role of PS revealed that financial considerations can diminish the strength of pro-environmental intentions. Specifically, the negative moderation of the SI - GPI relationship by PS suggests that individuals who strongly identify with environmental causes may still forgo green purchases due to affordability concerns (Yadav & Pathak, 2017; Lin & Niu, 2018). This underscores the dual burden of psychological intent and economic feasibility in sustainable decision-making. In price-sensitive markets, consumers are more likely to make purchasing decisions based on financial considerations rather than purely environmental motives. This finding emphasizes the need for policy interventions and market solutions that address both the economic and psychological barriers to green consumption, such as subsidies for eco-friendly products or increasing the affordability of sustainable alternatives.

Demographic trends within the study population predominantly female, urban, and composed of young adults also influenced green purchase intention (GPI). Female respondents demonstrated greater environmental concern, aligning with prior findings that women tend to exhibit stronger pro-environmental attitudes and behaviors (Xiao & McCright, 2015). Likewise, younger participants (ages 18–39) showed heightened GPI, consistent with global trends that suggest younger generations are more climate-aware and sustainability-oriented (Parker et al., 2020). Higher levels of education and international exposure were also associated with increased GPI, reinforcing earlier research that emphasizes the importance of socio-cultural learning, global awareness, and educational attainment in promoting sustainable consumption behaviors (Ghali-Zinoubi & Toukabri, 2019; Cheng et al., 2023).

This study thus reveals a complex interaction between personal, social, and economic drivers of green purchasing. While psychological factors like EA, SI, and PSE play a pivotal role, their impact is mediated by contextual constraints such as PS and demographic background. The findings extend TPB by illustrating how internal and external factors jointly shape sustainable behavior.

Conclusion

This study offers novel insights into the psychological and contextual drivers of green purchase intention (GPI) in Turkmenistan. By extension of the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB; Ajzen, 1991) model with the variables of environmental awareness (EA), self-identity (SI), perceived self-efficacy (PSE), and subjective norms (SN), and using price sensitivity (PS) as a moderating variable, this study attempts to provide a more culturally appropriate, detailed understanding of eco-consumer behaviour.

This research findings show that personal level factors especially PSE and SI are strong predictors of GPI. This is consistent with previous research that demonstrated individuals' belief in their ability to make a change prior (Yoong et al., 2018; Dubey et al., 2024), and that their self-concept with environmentalism have an affect on their purchasing intentions (Grębosz-Krawczyk et al., 2021). Although SN showed a negative relationship with GPI, its significance suggests that in some cultural contexts, social pressure may operate as a barrier rather than a motivator, reflecting deeper attitudinal or normative resistance to green practices (Minbashrazgah et al., 2017).

The moderating role of PS exposes an important tension: even consumers with high green awareness and identity may still refuse to act sustainably based on costs. This is in line with Ghali-Zinoubi and Toukabri (2019) who argue that price is the biggest barrier for green consumption in price sensitive markets. The results underscore that green intentions are not immune to economic realities, particularly in developing countries where income constraints are pronounced.

This study also highlights demographic effects: younger, urban, and international cohort were more likely to engage

with sustainable behavior, and women were even more environmentally aware consistent with global observations of gender consumption gaps for green intentions and behavior (Xiao & McCright, 2015; Parker et al., 2020). In this respect, it is likely that future sustainability campaigns will be designed to promote the change on those group, and remove barriers of cost, to reduce the intention-behavior gap.

Overall, this study builds on the TPB within the economic and demographic domain within the psychological and contextual model of green behavior. It not only fills a regional research gap but also offers practical insights for policymakers, educators, and businesses aiming to cultivate sustainable consumption in emerging economies. By addressing both personal motivation and situational barriers, sustainable change becomes not only a matter of awareness but also of access and empowerment.

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